

MEDICAL SCIENCES

FREQUENCY OF MECHANICAL AND TRAUMATIC DAMAGE TO ENAMEL AND DENTIN IN PERMANENT TEETH

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Abstract

Of significant interest for clinical dentistry is the high prevalence and intensity of non-carious dental lesions. Damage to hard tissues includes cracks in enamel and dentin.

According to many researchers, they occur in more than 90% of examined individuals [3–7]. Some authors attribute mechanical loads and trauma to the main causes of cracks [7, 13], others - temperature factors [13, 14]. The development of cracks can also be promoted by medical manipulations [5, 20, 21]. Cracks, being pathways for the penetration of microorganisms and proteolytic enzymes into hard tissues, play a role in the occurrence of caries and can cause pulp and periodontal diseases [2, 12, 13, 15]. Other researchers believe that the reasons for the formation of cracks are: age-related features, abrasion, depulpation and teeth whitening [1, 3, 4, 8, 9, 13]. Many authors associate the formation of cracks during tooth preparation with increased temperature, vibration of instruments and pressure exerted on the tooth [5, 13]. There is evidence of the formation of cracks due to polymerization shrinkage and contraction stresses arising in the “filling-tooth” system [11]. Classifications of cracks have been proposed depending on their location, depth, and direction [10]. The purpose of this study was to study the frequency of occurrence of cracks in enamel and dentin of all groups of teeth in people of different ages. We examined 222 patients aged 15 to 84 years who had an appointment with a dentist. Of these, 120 were women and 102 were men. The clinical examination of the patient consisted of collecting complaints and anamnesis, as well as a dental examination. In addition, the teeth were examined for the presence or absence of cracks, their direction, depth and color using intraoral light sources operating from a universal dental unit, staining the tooth surface with a 1% solution of methylene blue, drying with a dry cotton swab or a stream of warm air. Monocular and binocular magnifications with magnifications of 10* and 3.3*, as well as the transillumination method, were used. Analysis of dental status data indicates changes in the main indicators of dental health with age. Thus, the CP index increased from 5.78±0.51 in the first age group to 19.52±1.16 after 45 years. Characterized by a significant increase in the number of extracted teeth in the structure of the CP after 44 years. The results of the examination of the dentition

for the detection of cracks are presented in table. 1. According to data analysis, the average number of teeth examined for cracks was 22.07±0.45 and amounted to about 70% of the total number of teeth. There is a characteristic dependence on age. So, if the maximum number of teeth was available for examination in the first age group, then there are 2 fewer teeth at 30 years of age. At the age of 35–44, the number of examined teeth was 22.83±1.1; this figure decreases by 4.22 by the age of 50. After 65 years, less than half of the teeth can be examined due to the fact that the number of extracted teeth increases at this age. Among all teeth examined for cracks, on average, almost 75% were with cracks and 2 times less without them. The number of teeth on which cracks are not detected decreases almost 15 times in middle age compared to young people. At the same time, the number of teeth on which cracks are found increases (from 8.68±0.6 in 20 years to 21.54±1.04 in the group 35–44). After 30 years, more than 70% of accessible teeth had cracks and only one third were uncracked. The maximum number of teeth with cracks was recorded after 40 years, and in the group 45–64 all examined teeth had cracks. On average, for every 11 intact teeth with cracks, there were 5 carious and filled teeth. Almost 4 intact teeth with cracks were identified at the age of 20. By the age of 30, their number triples, and at the age of 35–44, more than 90% of intact teeth have cracks. After 50 years, the number of healthy teeth with cracks reaches 100%. In young people, the number of carious and filled teeth was 5.04±0.43; in the group 25–34, the number of carious and filled teeth reached its maximum value and amounted to 8.31±0.69. This is then followed by a decline to 2.31 at age 65. The decrease in the number of carious and filled teeth with age is explained by the increase in the number of extracted teeth and artificial crowns in older age groups. At the same time, cracks were found on all examined carious and filled teeth. Depending on the number of cracks, teeth with single and multiple cracks were distinguished. With age, along with an increase in the total number of teeth with cracks, the number of teeth with multiple cracks in-

creases. The number of teeth with single cracks increases from 8.4 in the first age group to 15.7 in the second. Then there is a gradual decrease in such teeth to 11.7 by the age of 40. 8.14 ± 0.61 teeth with single cracks are detected at 50 years of age and half as many in older people. In general, almost 60% with single and about 40% with multiple cracks in teeth are found among all those examined. At a young age, only 3% of teeth have multiple cracks, and at 30 years old their number increases 11 times and in the group 35–44 reaches 9.8. At least 10 teeth with multiple cracks are found after age 50, and approximately 75% of teeth have more than 3 cracks at older ages. Completed and unfinished types of cracks were distinguished by length. Depending on the visual signs, the following types of incomplete cracks were distinguished: Type I - not visible to the naked eye on intact, filled, carious teeth without the use of additional lighting, drying, optical systems (monocular and binocular magnifying glasses) or the use of transillumination (difficult to detect), thin, superficial, vertical, “crazy lines”; Type II - cracks that are visible to the naked eye with intraoral lighting and drying without the use of additional methods on intact, filled and carious teeth, deeper, vertical and oblique; Type III - cracks that are visible to the naked eye in normal lighting, pigmented, painted with methylene blue, deep, vertical, oblique, horizontal and combined. The distribution of different types of cracks on teeth is presented in Table. 2. On average, about 31% of intact teeth had type I cracks. 2% fewer teeth with cracks were found at age 50. The percentage of teeth with the first type of cracks decreases with age. Thus, the frequency of lesions decreases from $41.32 \pm 8.6\%$ in 15-year-olds to almost 2 times by the age of 70. Approximately the same proportion of such teeth is determined in the second and third age groups. The average incidence of damage to intact teeth by type 2 cracks was 53.7%. 10% less than the average value of such teeth was at 70 years old. Half of all teeth with cracks of this type were found by age 50 and 7% more in the middle age group. The maximum frequency of their detection was after 25 years and 5% less in young people. The frequency of damage to carious and filled teeth by type I cracks decreases almost 7 times from younger to older age, and averaged $18.30 \pm 14.9\%$. Teeth with this type of crack were 10% less than the average at 50 years of age. In the middle age group, the incidence of teeth with the first type of cracks was $14.29 \pm 5.92\%$, and one and a half times higher in 30-year-olds. By the age of 20, in $65.67 \pm 8.6\%$ of cases, carious and filled teeth with type II cracks were found. The incidence of lesions increases by 8.5% in the second group, and then decreases to 69% in middle age and to 50% at 50 years of age. More than 40% of teeth with the second type of cracks are observed in the elderly. The frequency of damage to carious and filled teeth by type III cracks increases from $1.98 \pm 8.6\%$ in young people to $51.95 \pm 5.38\%$ after 70. More than 16% of teeth with this type of cracks are detected, on average, in all those examined. There were the same number of them in the third group, and 4 times less in 30-year-olds. More than 40% of such teeth occur between the ages of 45–64 years. Consequently, all carious and

filled teeth at any age had cracks. The frequency of crack detection depending on the research method is presented in Table. 3. The number of cracks detected without the use of additional lighting increases with age from 0.004 ± 0.02 per tooth in 15-year-olds to 0.44 ± 1.76 after 50. Their number is 4 times less in the group 35–44 and they are detected almost 15 times less often in 30-year-olds. At least 1 crack on 1 examined tooth is detected during visual examination in the older age group. On average, the staining method allows you to see 0.16 more cracks per tooth. They are detected in the amount of 1.5 in elderly people, and 2 times less such cracks in 50 year olds. Their number increases from 0.02 ± 0.09 in young people to 0.18 ± 0.45 in middle age, and they are observed 2.5 times less often in the second group. On average, more than 75% of all cracks are detected by using additional lighting and drying the tooth surface. This method makes it possible to detect 2.78 ± 4.2 cracks per tooth in older people and 13 times less in the group 15–24. At the age of 30, their number increases to 0.68 ± 1.53 . Their number increases by another 0.7 by the age of 40, and 1.96 cracks are found per tooth when dried and illuminated in 50-year-olds. On average, the transillumination method made it possible to detect 1.83 ± 1.84 cracks on each examined tooth. In the group 65 and above, they were detected in maximum quantity and amounted to 3.47 ± 8.69 cracks. Their number was 10 times less in young people, and 3.5 times less common in those aged 30 years. Then the number of cracks doubles in the middle group and by another 0.78 after 50 years. In Fig. Figure 9 shows the frequency of crack detection using optical instruments. Analysis of the data shows that close, similar data on the number of cracks can be obtained using binocular and monocular loupes (1.6 and 1.5 on average, respectively). Their number is 2 times greater in older people and 6 times less in 20-year-olds. At least 2 cracks on 1 tooth are detected using optical instruments by the age of 50. Their number is 0.5 less in middle age, and they are 2 times less common in the second group compared to 40-year-olds.

Conclusions.

Thus, the results of the study indicate that cracks in the hard tissues of teeth can be detected at any age. Regardless of the diagnostic method, the number of detected cracks naturally increases with age. All carious and filled teeth have cracks, differing from intact teeth in a greater frequency and variety of directions. Most cracks become visible when additional lighting is used and the tooth surface is dried. It is necessary to note changes in the viewing angle and position of the light source, as well as the creation of “penumbra”, since the light is largely absorbed by normal enamel and completely reflected from cracks. The maximum number of cracks is detected when using binocular and monocular loupes and the transillumination method. Since most cracks are asymptomatic and difficult to diagnose, these methods can be recommended for detecting hidden damage to enamel and dentin.

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